

Energy-based Models are Zero-Shot Planners for Compositional Scene Rearrangement

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Introduction

If we teach a robot the concepts “*left/right/front of*”, can it generalize to “*place the apple in front of the duck, left of the avocado and right of the green bowl*”?

How can we build robots that:

- decompose complex instructions into familiar concepts,
- are robust to visual variations of the environment.

Scene Rearrangement via Energy Minimization

EBMs are trained on atomic concepts

Using as few as 10 demos!

EBMs are composable!

SREM is a modular framework for scene rearrangement:

- The instruction is first parsed into a list of calls to a vision-language grounder and energy-based models.
- The grounder locates the objects mentioned in the instruction.
- The energy-based models (EBMs) infer a goal configuration for all mentioned objects jointly.
- A policy moves the objects to the predicted goal locations.

Experimental setup:

- Training on individual concepts (e.g., “*make a line of fruits*”)
- Test of compositional instructions (e.g., “*put the red bowl to the right of the yellow cube and above the blue cylinder*”).

Why is joint optimization important?

Results

SREM better models the training tasks

Robust to visual variations

Zero-shot generalizes to compositional instructions

